

Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats

Deliverable 4.1

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 4.1 overview

Deliverable 4.1 *Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats* serves as a data descriptor, detailing the data acquisition processes and procedures involved in generating spatially and standardized sediment organic carbon (blue carbon) data for European seas. The data shows large variations in the sediment organic carbon content within biogenic habitats, with highest levels generally found in sediments of saltmarshes and seagrass habitats.

The blue carbon database forms background information for mapping of organic carbon levels in European seas, which is relevant for the designation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). In subsequent tasks, the blue carbon data will be analysed in relation to habitat and environmental characteristics to identify potential drivers of carbon levels and to develop a scoring system for blue carbon in European seas. The resulting blue carbon map will feed into MPA Europe's prioritisation tool and systematic conservation planning approach (WP5) to design MPA networks that maximize marine biodiversity and carbon stocks within the MPAs.

Biogenic habitats are defined under EUNIS as 3D physical structures created by living organisms (i.e. also called *biogenic engineers* or *bioengineers* or *habitat-forming species*). They include bivalve reefs, mussel beds, worm reefs, seagrass beds (*Posidonia oceanica*), maerl and cold water coral reefs. In this report we apply a similar but broader definition, which includes marine "vegetated biogenic habitats" growing on sedimentary seafloor (all seagrass habitats and saltmarsh habitats, see e.g. Boström et al. 2011) because these actively contribute to organic carbon sequestration and storage (Duarte et al. 2013). We make clear in the text where we address EUNIS biogenic habitats and where we address vegetated sediment habitats. It is important to note this report does not include a full list of biogenic habitats. **Non-biogenic habitats**, by contrast, are defined as habitats with all types of substrata (rock, mud, sand, etc.) that are not formed by living organisms.

Background

Marine sediments are one of the major organic carbon (OC) reservoirs on the planet and the efficiency of these sinks are important in regulating earth's climate (Larowe et al., 2020; Howard et al., 2023). Recent estimates suggest that, on a global scale, surface sediments (down to 5 cm) contain an OC reservoir of around $87,000 \pm 43,000$ Mt (Lee et al., 2019), while down to depths of 1 m the reservoir can be as large as 2.3 million Mt (Atwood et al., 2020). However, the sediment standing stocks and fate of OC vary considerably depending on location as well as on the temporal and spatial scales studied (Larowe et al., 2020). The capability of marine sediments to retain OC has intrigued biogeochemists for decades. It is only more recently that this subject, denoted "Blue Carbon" (defined by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) as "*all biologically-driven carbon fluxes and storage in marine systems that are amenable to management*"), has gained considerable attention within the wider marine research- and management communities, with a focus on the role of management of carbon-rich habitats to protect and increase their capacity to capture carbon dioxide and retain OC (Nellemann and Corcoran, 2009; Duarte et al., 2013; Howard et al., 2023). The protection of carbon sinks requires data on their location and size as well as knowledge on drivers.

In this report we present a database on total organic carbon (TOC) concentrations in marine sediments of the European seas, with a focus on those associated with biogenic habitats (*Deliverable 4.1 Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats*). The data from this report can, together with the report for Deliverable 4.2 (*Database of carbon storage in European marine non-biogenic sediment habitats*), be used to map blue carbon in European seas. The two deliverables share the same initial sections while their final section focuses on biogenic habitats and non-biogenic habitats, respectively.

The databases will, in a subsequent step, form the basis for analysing drivers of blue carbon and potentially assign blue carbon scores of different habitats based on identified relationships between blue carbon levels and the combination of environmental conditions (e.g., sheltered vs. wave exposed) and habitat (according to EUNIS as well as according to whether the seafloor is vegetated or not). This integrative knowledge will inform regional and national policymakers on how to design MPA networks to maximise protection of blue carbon habitats (see Howard et al., 2023) while also maximizing the protection of biodiversity within the MPAs.

Methods

Rationale for data included

Vegetated habitats such as saltmarshes, mangroves, seagrass meadows have been highlighted as major contributors to carbon sequestration and storage within their habitat while also having positive impact on biodiversity, coastal protection, fisheries, and water quality (Duarte et al., 2013; Macreadie et al., 2021). By contrast, most macroalgae dominate rocky shores which do not sequester carbon, but they are carbon donors to sinks beyond their habitats (Krause-Jensen & Duarte 2016). The main focus in the Blue Carbon context has been on the productive vegetated coastal habitats that have a high carbon sequestration per unit area. However, since they only occur on the seafloor within the photic zone, their geographic distribution is small compared to the area of sediments in the ocean (Jacquemont et al., 2022, Luisetti et al., 2019). This highlights the importance of a better understanding of OC storage in all marine sediments, as well as identifying the controlling factors that influence the size of these stocks.

Data compilation

In April 2023, the research community was invited to [contribute data to establish a Euro-Carbon database](#) of TOC stocks in marine sediments, i.e., blue carbon. Researchers were encouraged to submit both previously published and unpublished data (Figure 1). For this purpose, we created a template that all contributors used. The current version of the database contains the data received so far from the research community. The final database will, in addition, encompass data from existing databases and scientific literature, meaning that the current overview represents preliminary results. The compiled data were collected, analysed and processed by different laboratories. Key information on sampling sites, methods and analytical techniques were provided along with the data.

In this database we only included measurements which have directly determined the TOC content, and we do therefore not include, e.g., estimates obtained by the loss on ignition (LOI) technique. This is because the relationship between TOC and LOI is highly variable as it depends on sediment composition (e.g., clay and salt content) (Santisteban et al., 2004).

Figure 1. The MPA Europe Euro-Carbon database at a first glance. Overview of the data received until 31st of October 2023.

In our data call we asked the data contributors to provide information on the following variables:

- Country
- Habitat
- Sample ID
- Location name, Station ID, Core ID
- Year of sampling
- Month of sampling
- Sampling day
- Latitude of measurement (in decimal degrees)
- Longitude of measurement (in decimal degrees)
- Water depth (m) at which the sediment core was obtained
- Temperature (°C)

- Salinity
- Depth interval of the sediment sample analysed compacted (cm)
- Depth interval of the sediment sample analysed decompacted (cm)
- Sediment porosity (%)
- Sediment water content (%)
- Sediment dry bulk density (g cm^{-3})
- Sediment dry bulk density flag (corrected for compaction/uncorrected for compaction)
- Organic matter (OM) (%)
- TOC (% or g cm^{-3} (dry weight))
- Carbon stable isotope ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in ‰) content
- Total nitrogen (TN) content (% or g cm^{-3} (dry weight))
- Nitrogen stable isotope ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$ in ‰) content
- Total phosphorus (TP) content (% or g cm^{-3} (dry weight))
- Carbon Reactivity Index (CRI) ranging from 0 (Organic matter is fully biodegradable) to 1 (Organic matter is non-biodegradable)
- Core dating
 - Mass accumulation rate ($\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$)
 - Sediment accumulation rate (mm year^{-1})
 - Carbon accumulation rate ($\text{g C m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$)
 - Total ^{210}Pb activity (Bq kg^{-1})
 - Excess ^{210}Pb activity (Bq kg^{-1})
 - Supported ^{210}Pb activity (Bq kg^{-1})
 - ^{14}C age (years) and ^{14}C material
- Sediment grain size (<0.063mm, 0.063-0.25mm, 0.25-0.5mm, 0.5-1mm, >1mm)
- Methods for how data was obtained as well as the sediment sampling device.
- Data originator
- Originator institution
- Contact of data originator
- Publications

Not all variables were available for all TOC data received.

Quality control (QC) of datasets is crucial to ensure their reliability and usefulness. Thus, we have not included data that were deemed compromised. Nonetheless, a degree of uncertainty within the dataset was accepted given multiple groups have been involved in the data compilation. Some obvious errors were corrected (e.g., clearly inaccurate longitudes or latitudes were corrected) while others could not be corrected (e.g., unrealistic high TOC values) and were consequently excluded from the database. Prior to excluding observations that were suspected to be outliers, we contacted the data contributors to seek confirmation of the observations. In our database, we carefully avoided overly strict criteria, known as “data grooming”, which could potentially overlook genuine patterns and changes in the dataset that may be important over longer temporal and/or wider spatial scales. Marine sediments represent a wide range of environmental conditions, influenced by factors such as local anthropogenic activities and, consequently, the TOC data points may encompass a wide concentration range.

In some cases, data contributors added “Intertidal” to the “Water depth” column instead of a numeric value. To include these data points in numeric depth categories, we replaced this information with a depth between –1 m and 0 m depending on the habitat. Intertidal eelgrass was set to 0 m, unvegetated

tidal flat, low-tidal level saltmarshes (low marsh) and intermediate-level saltmarshes were set to -0.5 m, while high-tidal level saltmarshes (high marsh) were set to -1 m. Additionally, in some cases, the sediment data provided did not fit into the 5 grain size categories of the template. In these cases, the data were instead divided into two general categories: mud (< 0.063 mm) and sand (> 0.063 mm).

Common field and analytical procedures

Depending on the research focus and demands as well as technical capability, a wide range of sampling techniques have been used to collect sediment cores, including a whole range of sediment corers (e.g. piston corer, box corer). The different sampling techniques and strategies used may, to some extent, have impacted the measured TOC content, but given the large dataset, we assume that such effects will be limited relative to overall patterns in data. However, it is established that sample decompaction and at greater water depths depressurization can impact the intactness of the obtained sediment cores and thereby the results. Following sampling, retrieved sediment cores were typically divided into fixed sections based on depth ranges relevant to the study focus and measured variables.

After core retrieval and sectioning of the sediments, physical properties (water content, porosity, grain size, and density) were commonly measured. These factors reflect the physical environment of the sediment and influence the chemical and biological conditions. The water content of the sediment was normally quantified as the difference in weight before and after drying the sediment sample to constant weight. Sediment porosity has been defined as the volume of water-filled void (“empty”) space compared to the total volume. Porosity is normally calculated from wet weights and densities of the sediment. The grain size distribution is important as it determines the porosity, especially in fine-grained sediment where porosity is controlled by grain size and mineralogy (Burdige, 2007). Grain size is commonly measured using a particle size analyser. Bulk dry density is defined as the mass of the total dry sediment divided by the total sample volume. Bulk dry densities vary from close to 1 (high porosity sediment) to > 2 (low porosity sediments) and is commonly calculated by sampling a known volume of sediment and drying the sediment to a constant weight, after removing large shells, stones etc. (Howard et al., 2014).

The two most common methods used to determine sediment TOC content rely on conversion of OC into CO_2 using either wet chemical or high temperature oxidation techniques. The wet oxidation technique (e.g., persulfate oxidation) uses chemicals (e.g., potassium dichromate and sulfuric acid) to convert TOC into CO_2 which is subsequently quantified. The steps involved and the use of these methods for marine sediments have been outlined in multiple previous studies, e.g., Buchanan and Kain (1971), Byers et al. (1978). The high temperature oxidation technique uses a “flash combustion” of sediment TOC to oxidize OC to CO_2 , which is then detected using an infrared (NDIR) gas analyser. Both the wet oxidation and high temperature oxidation techniques rely upon the separation of organic from inorganic carbon forms for an accurate quantification of TOC. Earlier studies achieved separation of inorganic carbon and OC by heating the sediment to ash (above 1050°C). More recently, acidification has been used to remove carbonates, but caution should be applied as adding too much acid can lead to particle dissolution and loss of TOC (Weliky et al., 1983; Van Iperen and Helder, 1985). TOC data obtained in high-carbonate sediments, such as mussel beds, might have a higher analytical error due to the incomplete removal of carbonates (e.g. Van Iperen and Helder, 1985). Determination of the sediment TN content relies, as for TOC, on either a wet chemical oxidation or high-temperature oxidation techniques. In the wet chemical oxidation approach, both organic and inorganic N compounds are oxidised to inorganic nutrients which are then subsequently quantified through a colorimetric method (Avramidis et al., 2015). In the high temperature combustion approach, TN concentrations are determined based on conversion into nitrogen oxides which are then determined by chemiluminescent emission using a nitric oxide detector. The high-temperature technique generally measures simultaneously the TOC and TN

content on the same sample as the analysers are fitted in series on a CHN elemental analyser (Verardo et al., 1990). Phosphorus forms in marine sediments are redox-dependent. When oxic conditions prevail, substantial amounts of P are retained in the sediment through adsorption to iron oxides (e.g. Krom and Berner, 1980). In contrast, when anoxic conditions are present, inorganic forms dominate (Ruttenberg, 2004). Therefore, in studies focusing on sediment P, often several different P forms are measured (Van Helmond et al., 2020; Ruttenberg, 1992). The TP included here was generally determined by initially using a digestion (e.g., microwave or high temperature) and/or a chemical digestion step (Ruttenberg, 1992). Thereafter, the total inorganic phosphorus concentrations are determined.

The stable isotope content of C ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and N ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) have frequently been used to determine the organic matter origin and it is commonly analysed by nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR) or mass spectrometry (MS) which often is coupled in series with a CHN elemental analyser (Kennedy et al., 2005).

To report the accumulation rate as well as the age of the sediment, two dating techniques were considered; analysing the sediment content of lead 210 (^{210}Pb) or Carbon-14 (^{14}C). The ^{210}Pb -dating is conducted using alpha spectrometry and the decay of excess ^{210}Pb activity is used to determine the sediment accumulation rate. This method can be used to determine sediment deposits that are up to approximately 150 years old. The ^{14}C -dating method is based on the fact that living organisms incorporate radioactive carbon from the atmosphere. When the organisms die, they stop incorporating new carbon and start to decay; here the known half-life of the ^{14}C isotope can be used together with the content to determine time elapsed since death. The method can date organic materials up to around 50,000 years old.

The data template including all data received were supplemented with information about the substrata type based on EUNIS 2019 classification of seabed habitats. The .xlsx file was converted into .csv file and subsequently into geospatial shapefile with the format .shp. Spatial Join tool in ArcMap 10.1 was used to extract information (See Table 1). Based on EUNIS 2019 classification of seabed habitats, the sediments included in this current dataset were primarily associated with the biocenosis of the seagrass *Posidonia oceanica* (MB252), with very few data points from Atlantic infralittoral *Serpula vermicularis* reefs (MB.2212), *Limaria hians* beds in tide-swept Atlantic infralittoral muddy mixed sediment (MB.2221), and bivalve reefs in the Atlantic infralittoral zone (MB222). Overall, a total of 153 biogenic data points (OC average of top 10 cm sediment) are represented in the database.

Results

Sediment organic carbon

From our data call, we received in total 34,815 data entries (updated on the 31st of October 2023) of which 25,751 consisted of TOC values that were specified as “directly measured”. Averaging the TOC values from the top 10 cm of each sediment core, we obtained 6,847 unique datapoints (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Map showing the spatial distribution of the sediment organic carbon (OC in %) observations included in the MPA Europe Euro-Carbon database. The MPA Europe study area is in blue.

The dry bulk density, which is essential for calculating precise volume-based organic carbon (OC) stock, was only reported in a subset (38%) of the received OC data. Estimates of OC-sequestration rates were also only available from a subset (~5 %) of samples. Therefore, this report focuses on % OC content rather than OC-stocks. Overall, the OC content varied between 0.0 and 32 % (mean: 1.9 ± 2.1 %; median: 1.3 %, Figure 3A, Table 2). When considering only the top 10 cm of the sediment (54% of data; $n = 13652$), the range (0 to 32%) and average and median (mean: 1.9 ± 2.2 , median: 1.2) were not different from the whole dataset (Table 2). Because the sediment data represented different depth intervals between datasets, we chose to show a dataset of average OC values representing the surface 10 cm of the sediment in our further analysis (Figure 3B, Table 2 OC-Average top 10 cm).

Figure 3. Histograms showing the distribution of observations for (A) all % organic carbon (OC %) observations and (B) the averaged content in the top 10 cm of the sediment. **Note:** Due to the large number of observations at low OC% values (further to the left on the x-axis) single/few observations with higher content (further right on the x-axis) are not visible.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for the percentage of organic carbon (%OC) dataset. The minimum, maximum, average values (\pm standard deviation, SD), median, coefficient of variance (CV), 25th and 75th percentiles (%tiles) and number of samples are shown for the whole dataset (**All**), the top 10 cm of the sediment (**Top 10 cm**) and the average of the top 10 cm sediment layer (**Average Top 10 cm**).

Organic carbon			
	All (%)	Top 10 cm (%)	Average top 10 cm (%)
Minimum	< 0.01	< 0.01	< 0.01
Maximum	31.84	31.84	22.10
Average \pm SD	1.86 ± 2.06	1.88 ± 2.17	1.81 ± 2.08
Median	1.27	1.23	1.20
CV	110	115	115
25%tiles	0.50	0.54	0.53
75%tiles	2.33	2.29	2.23
Number of samples	25751	13652	6847

Restricting our analysis to the average top 10 cm, OC samples represented water depths between -1 m (i.e. above mean tidal level) and 5,576 m (mean: 304 ± 687 m, median: 68 m; Table 3) with highest number of samples and highest range of OC content in shallower water (Figure 4). Sediment with a high mud content and a low bulk density also represented high OC content (Figure 4).

Figure 4. X-Y plots displaying relationships between the averaged sediment % organic carbon (% OC) levels in the top 10 cm with (A) bulk density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$), (B) mud $< 0.06\mu\text{m}$ content (%), and (C) sampling station water depth (m).

Table 3. Summary of the environmental variables in the 10 cm of the sediment; bulk density, mud content and water depth. SD= standard deviation, CV= coefficient of variation; 25th and 75th percentiles (%tiles). A negative water depths indicated that the samples were collected above mean tidal level).

	Bulk density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$)	Mud (<0.063mm) (%)	Water depth (m)
Minimum	0.04	0.0	-1
Maximum	4.39	99.8	5576
Average \pm SD	1.0 ± 0.5	27.7 ± 36.7	304 ± 687
Median	1.05	3.3	68.2
CV	51.2%	132.7%	225%
25%tiles	0.57	1.0	20
75%tiles	1.34	59.6	246.4
Number of samples	1167	1014	6698

Biogenic habitats

The % OC contents were on average higher in sediments of the EUNIS biogenic habitats (average: 3.98 ± 4.07 , median: 2.46) compared with the EUNIS non-biogenic habitats (average: 1.49 ± 1.53 , median: 1.05) (Figure 5A).

Figure 5. Box plots of the averaged organic carbon content (OC %) in the top 10 cm of the sediment for (A) habitats divided according to EUNIS into biogenic habitats (in this case *Posidonia oceanica* (MB252), Atlantic infralittoral *Serpula vermicularis* reefs (MB2212), *Limaria hians* beds in tide-swept Atlantic infralittoral muddy mixed sediment (MB2221) and bivalve reefs in the Atlantic infralittoral zone (MB222)) and non-biogenic habitats; and (B) marine vegetated biogenic habitats (broader definition), here including saltmarsh, seagrass, and mixed seagrass and seaweed. The lines represent median values, the limits of the boxes represent 25-75 percentiles, and the whiskers extend from the limit of the box to the largest or smallest value but no further than $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ (inter quartile range). NA = EUNIS habitat information not available.

Table 4. Summary statistics for the average organic carbon (OC %) content in the top 10 cm of the sediment for (A) biogenic and non-biogenic habitats according to EUNIS definition and (B) marine vegetated biogenic habitats (broader definition), here including saltmarsh, seagrass, and mixed seagrass and seaweed habitats. Coefficient of variance (CV), 25th and 75th percentiles (%tiles) and number of samples (N) are shown. NA= sediment information not available.

Organic carbon								
	Minimum	Maximum	Average \pm SD	Median	CV	25% tiles	75% tiles	N
A								
Biogenic	0.14	21.0	3.98 \pm 4.07	2.46	102.3	1.14	5.12	153
Non-biogenic	0	20.3	1.49 \pm 1.53	1.05	102.7	0.48	2.02	4040
NA	0.02	22.1	2.18 \pm 2.47	1.02	113.3	0.64	2.70	2604
B								
Saltmarsh	0.21	16.6	3.22 \pm 3.45	2.48	107.1	0.28	4.10	156
Seagrass	0	21.0	2.77 \pm 3.59	1.30	129.6	0.29	3.71	629
Mixed seagrass, seaweed	1.03	8.8	2.51 \pm 2.17	1.89	86.5	1.38	2.48	21

Our data show that within the vegetated biogenic habitats there was large variation in the % OC content, with saltmarshes (3.22 \pm 3.45) having the highest content in the top 10 cm of the sediment followed by seagrasses (2.77 \pm 3.59) and then mixed seagrass and seaweed (2.51 \pm 2.17) (Table 4, Figure 5B). Within the vegetated biogenic habitats the coefficient of variation (CV, i.e., dispersion of the data around the mean) was highest for seagrasses followed by saltmarshes. This demonstrates that the % OC content is especially variable in these habitats likely due to differences in the biological and physical controls (Table 4). See Deliverable 4.2 (*Database of carbon storage in European marine non-biogenic sediment habitats*) for further information on non-biogenic habitats.

The highest average OC contents, when considering seagrasses at a species level, were measured in *Posidonia oceanica* (4.75 \pm 4.25) and *Zostera marina* (3.86 \pm 3.81) habitats (Table 5; Figure 6). The CV was particularly high for Zosteraceae species, suggesting large regional differences (Table 5), e.g. influenced by physical forcing, such as currents. It should be noted that *Posidonia* has a preferred sediment and is, therefore, a specific biogenic substratum according to the EUNIS definition in contrast to *Zostera* species which grow on various sediments. A recent global analysis of drivers of OC stocks in seagrass sediments identified species traits and geomorphic setting as key drivers, and highlighted *Posidonia oceanica* and other large and persistent species as those having the largest carbon stocks (Kennedy et al. 2022).

Figure 6. Box plot of the average organic carbon OC (%) content in the top 10 cm of sediment for the different seagrass species and/or seaweed bed habitats. This information was only available for 59% of the seagrass data. No information was available at species level for saltmarshes, and they are therefore not included in this plot. The lines represent median values, the limits of the boxes represent 25-75 percentiles, and the whiskers extends from the limit of the box to the largest/smallest value but no further than 1.5*IQR (inter quartile range).

Table 5. Summary statistics for the average organic carbon (OC %) content in the top 10 cm of the sediments in different seagrass species and/or seaweed beds. The average values (\pm standard deviation, SD), median, coefficient of variance (CV), 25th and 75th percentiles (%tiles) and number of samples (N) are presented.

Seagrass species	Organic carbon							
	Minimum	Maximum	Average \pm SD	Median	CV	25% tiles	75% tiles	N
<i>Zostera marina</i>	0.08	13.80	3.86 \pm 3.81	2.57	98.70	0.37	6.38	183
<i>Nanozostera noltei</i>	0.17	2.09	0.68 \pm 0.60	0.44	87.99	0.33	0.79	9
Zosteraceae species	0.056	5.57	0.76 \pm 1.59	0.19	209.21	0.10	0.25	14
<i>Cymodocea nodosa</i>	0.15	4.74	1.07 \pm 1.17	0.46	109.35	0.26	1.55	42
Mixed seagrass, seaweed	0.34	8.84	2.62 \pm 3.14	0.83	119.85	0.53	3.29	12
<i>Posidonia oceanica</i>	0.24	21.00	4.75 \pm 4.25	3.38	89.47	1.56	6.38	120

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All data contributors are listed in Appendix 1.

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